

Simulation and experimental validation of single-phase series active power filter using PI and backstepping nonlinear controllers

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ABSTRACT

Nowadays, power distribution networks are focus mainly on power quality issues. Among the power disturbances, sag, swell and voltage harmonics are studied and deliberated in this research paper. These problems have negative impacts especially on the sensitive load, which have to be protected and secured against these problems. Therefore, to solve such disturbances, the series active power filter (SAPF) can be an efficient solution, which is used to compensate the voltage difference and to reduce the problem's effects on the power system. In this paper, the SAPF is simulated and experimentally validated, where two control methods are used to control the applied disturbances; which are classical proportional integral PI and nonlinear backstepping controllers. The control structure of the SAPF aims to reduce the error of the injection voltage closed loop, in addition to reduce the total harmonic distortion (THD) values below 5% and within the specified ranges of the international IEEE-519 standard. From simulation results, the backstepping nonlinear controller has reacted more robustly and efficiently than the conventional PI controller.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Given the demand of improving the power quality especially in industry, where the critical equipment and sensitive loads are widely used and their power supply should not interrupted. Here, uninterrupted, clean and regulated power supply is required when feeding loads that have important tasks. In other hand, most common voltage disturbances appear in alternative current appliances (AC) providing a reduction in voltage amplitude known as sag. Thus, sag and interruptions provide most of the industrial problems (90%) that affect their supply quality [1]. Other, swell problem is also among disturbances that affect the power quality, which is defined by a rising in voltage amplitude above its nominal value [2]. In addition, harmonic distortion can provide huge problems in the whole of the power conversion chain such as heating the system components, mechanical oscillations, unpredictable behavior of protecting devices, and may cause damage [3, 4].

Due to these problems, it is necessary to approve protecting devices and effective solution to solve such disturbances. In this paper, we focus on series active power filter (APFS) in order to mitigate sag-swell and harmonics [5-8] that affect our system. Thus, a serie compensator inserted between the source and

the load called dynamic voltage restorer (DVR) is also implemented in this work to protect operating voltage of sensitive and critical appliances against sag problem especially [9-12]. APFS have the same topology as the active filter, with an excellent dynamic capability to restore the load voltage to its nominal value within a few milliseconds as well providing power disruption to the supplied loads. In other researches, the series topology aims to compensate the sag with active power [13]. In power quality domain, various papers have used classical and intelligent controllers in order to improve the stability, robustness and excellent dynamic response of the APFS as mentioned in [4-18]. The control strategies used in this paper such as PI, FLC, and SMC present robust and efficient results with different THD ratio, where SMC has provided the best ratio with 3%. Models of the three controllers are developed mathematically as cited in various works such as [19-24], and adapted to our system topology.

This paper provides a new method for applying an adaptive backstepping controller in APFS and its operating principle. The control method based on a nonlinear backstepping controller is used to compensate the voltage sags and swells in low and medium voltage distribution systems [25]. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 1, presents the APFS model with modeling of the power system, section 2 focuses on the control strategies with a comparative study between the used strategies and finally, this paper ends with a conclusion.

2. DESCRIPTION OF THE SYSTEM

In this part, a brief description of the principal of the system element is mentioned.

2.1. Series active power filter APFS

In this paper, the studied system is composed mainly by three blocks, a programmable AC source to provide sag-swell and harmonics voltage scenarios, a sensitive load (medical equipment) and APFS. The APFS contains a single-phase PWM voltage source inverter in order to inject the compensating voltage by an injection transformer and an L_f , C_f second order filter to eliminate high frequency caused by inverter switching actions. This inverter is supplied by a DC source as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Single-phase series active power filter (APFS)

2.2. Modeling of the APFS system

This section deals with the mathematical modeling of the series active power filter APFS. The full structure of the APFS can be represented by a converter as shown in Figure 2, where Kirchhoff's voltage law (KVL) is applied to the AC closed circuit to get the following mathematical expression by [5]. The SAPF model shown in Figure 2 is modeled and represented by the following state space representation: Where x_1 and x_2 are the filter capacitor voltage V_C and the filter inductor current i_{L_f} respectively.

$$mv_0 = i_L R_f + L_f \frac{di_L}{dt} + v_{inj} \quad (1)$$

$$v_{inj} = i_c R_c + \frac{1}{C_f} \int (i_c dt) \quad (2)$$

With:

m : Control input to the series converter

i_L : Inductor current of the series converter

v_{inj} : Output voltage of the series converter

v_0 : DC link voltage

L_f : Filte inductance

C_f : Filte capacitance

R_f : Equivalent series resistance (ESR) of inductor

R_c : (ESR) of capacitor

Figure 2. Equivalent circuit of series converter

$$\hat{m}(s)V_0 = \hat{i}_L(s)(R_f + sL_f) + \hat{v}_{inj}(s) \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{v}_{inj}(s) = \hat{i}_c(s) \left(R_c + \frac{1}{sC_f} \right) \quad (4)$$

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{1}{C} x_2 - \frac{1}{C} i_L \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{x}_1 = \frac{1}{C} x_2 - \frac{1}{C} i_L \quad (6)$$

3. CONTROL STRATEGIES OF THE SYSTEM

The control strategies used in this work are PI and Backstepping Nonlinear controllers. Thus, a comparative study is made between the two methods in order to improve their performance and robustness in power quality. The two methods are described separately as follow:

3.1. Proportional integrator PI controller

The controller structure is based on a closed-control loop to regulate the injected voltage of the SAPF, where PWM signal is generated to the switching devices (IGBT) of the voltage source inverter VSI [7]. The PI controller can be defined by the mathematical expression of the transfer function in (7).

$$H_i(s) = K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} \quad (7)$$

The voltage error denoted ϵ is defined by the difference between the reference and the instantaneous values of the injection voltage. Therefore, PI controller determines instantaneous values of the error without considering their divergence and perturbations, which is defined by the derivate of the error $\Delta \epsilon$ [7]. The transfer function of voltage-closed loop of the VSI is defined by (8):

$$G_{vse}(s) = \frac{\hat{v}_{inj}(s)}{\hat{i}_c(s)} \tag{8}$$

Figure 3 depicts the difference between the reference value of the injected voltage and its real-time operating value, which is the error signal and the input to the selected controller (PI). This voltage error is treated by the controller to generate the appropriate signal command to the switching devices (Mosfet) via the PWM generator. Thus, the obtained signal commands aim to provide the required injected voltage by the inverter to compensate for the error of the voltage.

Figure 3. Controller PI with PWM and VSC

3.2. Backstepping nonlinear control of APFS

The backstepping control a nonlinear method based on lyapunov function, which can be considered as a passivation output with a storage function. Thus, this control method is a recursive design methodology that involves a systematic construction of feedback control laws and associated Lyapunov functions. The controller design can be reached in a number of steps that does not exceed the system order [25]. In this part the APFS system based on the proposed adaptive backstepping nonlinear controller and single-phase (levels) voltage source inverter. General block diagram of the system is shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. General block diagram of the adaptive nonlinear backstepping controller for APFS system

The control objective is to enforce the system to inject a compensation voltage V_c represented by the state space variable x_1 . This injected voltage is the difference voltage between the reference V_r and the instantaneous system voltage V_s , this drop voltage can be defined by u . In addition, the control problem caused by the nonminimum phase nature of the power converter is solved according to the indirect approach, where the direct output voltage regulation is unfeasible [25-28]. The controller design is given below in two main steps because of the order of the studied system (3, 4):

Step 1: The output voltage error is defined by: $y_1 = x_1 - u$. Then, deviating y_1 and substituting it from (5), we get:

$$\dot{y}_1 = \dot{x}_1 - \dot{u} = \frac{1}{C}x_2 - \frac{1}{C}i_L - \dot{u} \quad (9)$$

where the term x_2/C can be a virtual control input. From (5), we get the following:

$$\dot{y}_1 = -\alpha_1 y_1 \quad (\alpha_1 > 0)$$

$$\frac{x_2}{C} = -\alpha_1 y_1 + \frac{1}{C}i_L + \dot{u}$$

where, α is a design parameter. While x_2/C is not an effective input for the control design, the (9) is not valid for all value of the time ($t \geq 0$). Hence, the desired value of the term x_2/C can be defined by:

$$\beta_1 = \alpha_1 y_1 + \frac{1}{C}i_L + \dot{u} \quad (10)$$

$$y_2 = \frac{x_2}{C} - \beta_1 \quad (11)$$

where β is the stabilization function. Then, if the error or $y_1 = (x_1 - u)$ is vanishing asymptotically, so the control objective is reached. Therefore, replacing x_2/C in (5) by $(y_2 + \beta_1)$, and then substituting from (10), we can get:

$$\dot{y}_1 = -\alpha_1 y_1 + y_2 \quad (12)$$

Step 2: In this step we derivate the error y_2 , and substituting from (6) and (9), we get the following expression:

$$\dot{y}_2 = -\frac{1}{LC}x_1 + \frac{1}{LC}v_i - \dot{\beta}_1 \quad (13)$$

From (7), we get:

$$\dot{\beta}_1 = \alpha_1^2 y_1 - \alpha_1 y_2 + \frac{1}{C}i_L + \ddot{u} \quad (14)$$

Then, substituting from (10), we get:

$$\dot{y}_2 = -\frac{1}{LC}x_1 + \frac{1}{LC}v_1 - \alpha_1^2 y_1 + \alpha_1 y_2 + \frac{1}{C}i_L - \ddot{u} \quad (15)$$

By choosing the following function $V = (y_1^2 + y_2^2)$, we can derivate the state (y_1, y_2) to zero, where the time variation of the function V along the (y_1, y_2) trajectory is expressed as follow:

$$\dot{V} = y_1 \dot{y}_1 + y_2 \dot{y}_2$$

Table 1. Electrical parameters

Parameters	Values
Source voltage frequency f	50 Hz
Source voltage Vs	5.7 Vrms
Load resistance RL	12.3 Ω
Cf (LC filter inductance)	1 nF
Lf(LC filter capacitance)	9 mH
Transformer	12V/ 230V/ 1 KVA
DC-bus capacitor, DC-bus reference voltage	2200 uF- Vdc*=35V
Kp, Ki Simulation results	Kp =7.2-Ki=33
Kp, Ki Experimental results	Kp =8.8-Ki=4,24

Figure 6. Simulation voltage waveforms for PI controller

Figure 7. Simulation voltage waveforms for backstepping nonlinear controller

(a)

(b)

Figure 8. Spectral analysis for PI controller of the (a) source voltage, (b) load voltage

(a)

(b)

Figure 9. Spectral analysis for backstepping nonlinear controller of the (a) source voltage, (b) load voltage

4.2. Experimental results

The experimental results to validate the simulation tests and improve the robustness of the used control methods. The experimental test has realized and elaborated in Smart Grid and Renewable Energies Laboratory (SGRE-Lab) in the University of TAHRI Mohamed-Béchar-Algeria. The experimental prototype includes a dSPACE card 1104 platform Texas Instrument with a TMS32F240 DSP connected with a PC (pentium) in order to enable automatic implementation of the control methods directly from Matlab Simulink as illustrated in Figure 10. Thus, the test bench consists of a voltage inverter, an inductor, an injection transformer, Hall current/voltage sensors, linear load and a programmed source. The PWM switching gates were selected 15 KHz, which are generated from the Dspace card in real time experimental tests. Thus, a linear load was selected. As seen, the APFS has the ability to mitigate voltage harmonics provided by the grid and supplied to the connected load. The voltage harmonics are provided by the voltage inverter, which was connected in parallel with the source voltage. Figure 11 depicts the waveforms of the source, the load and the injected voltages during the experimental test taking into consideration normal operating mode (before and after applying the selected issue), and during the application of the selected issue (sag).

Figure 10. The photograph of the shunt APFS prototype

Figure 11. Experimental voltage waveforms for PI Controller

As mentioned in Figure 12, the spectral analysis of the source voltage was about 46.4% and the load voltage was 4.8% using the PI controller. Then, Figure 13 support these results with the experimental obtained curves of the injected voltage while tracking its reference value during the applied sag phenomena during [5.6 s-6.3 s]. In the previous paper [4, 29], fuzzy logic FLC and sliding mode SMC controllers have presented satisfactor results compared with the classical PI, where the THD values after the correction were about 4%-3.8% respectively. Figure 14 presents the waveforms of the voltages using the SMC method. In this paper, using backstepping nonlinear controller, the obtained results are unique and better than the previously applied methods. Exactly, the THD was about 3% during the application of the same issue and during the same period as seen in Figure 15. Therefore, the injected voltage was more efficient following the reference value as seen in Figure 16.

(a)

(b)

Figure 12. Spectral analysis of the (a) source voltage, (b) load voltage for Pi controller

Figure 13. Experimental voltage waveforms for PI controller

Figure 14. Experimental voltage waveforms for backstepping nonlinear controller

Figure 15. Spectral analysis of the (a) source voltage, (b) load voltage for backstepping nonlinear controller.

Figure 16. Experimental voltage waveforms for backstepping nonlinear controller

It seems clearly that the application of the backstepping non-linear control method has ameliorated the performance of the SAPF when eliminating the voltage harmonics caused by the programmable source. As seen in Figures 15 and 16, the injected voltage by the SAPF via the injection transformer has followed its reference value efficiently with the backstepping compared by the conventional PI controller. As a comparison between the two controllers, the injected voltage using the backstepping controller is characterized by its fast response time during transient period, with a negligible debasement compared with the PI. Hence, the backstepping has proven less voltage error compared with the PI due to its tuned gains represented by alpha α and beta β .

5. CONCLUSION

Through this brief study, we have presented a topic about improving the quality of energy using the series active power filter APFS. The APFS has presented fast and specific reactions with the voltage perturbation phenomenon such as harmonics. As previously explained, the used control methods were Backstepping nonlinear, which have been chosen to show the reaction of APFS with perturbations using classical and nonlinear control methods. In this study, we focused only on two parameters, which are the waveform of source and load voltages and the THD ratio. Thus, the controllers have presented excellent results in both simulation and experimental tests, with respecting to the norms of the IEEE 519 standard. Exactly, the three methods have compensated the harmonics voltages by the filter, while keeping a sinusoidal waveform of the load voltage despite the perturbation. In addition, among these controllers, the backstepping nonlinear has improved the lowest THD value compared with PI controller due to the robustness of its control structure. This work can be considered as a continuation of the previous research paper, where we have presented more improvement of the power quality with the Backstepping nonlinear.

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